

Appendix A: The X-HESS sample

The AGNs included in the X-HESS sample are listed in Table A.1, where the values of redshift, black hole mass and bolometric luminosity are drawn from the Rakshit et al. (2020) catalogue, unless otherwise stated. The values of λ_{Edd} reported in Table A.1 are calculated as the ratio of the bolometric to Eddington luminosity, $L_{\text{Edd}} = 1.26 \times 10^{38} (M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\odot})$ erg/s, where M_{BH} represents the fiducial estimate of the black hole mass based on the FWHM of either $\text{H}\beta$ or Mg II .

References

- Bischetti, M., Piconcelli, E., Vietri, G., et al. 2017, A&A, 598, A122
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Marziani, P. & Sulentic, J. W. 2014, MNRAS, 442, 1211
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Table A.1: X-HESS: comprehensive AGN list and their general properties.

ID	SDSS Name	RA	DEC	$N_{\text{H,gal}}$	$E(B - V)_{\text{int}}$	z	$\log(M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\odot})$	$\log(L_{\text{bol}}/\text{erg s}^{-1})$	λ_{Edd}	N_{epo}
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
1	J094610.71+095226.3	146.54	9.87	2.36	0.02	0.697	7.5	45.6	1.1	15
2	J095847.88+690532.7	149.70	69.09	7.00	<0.01	1.2882	9.1	47.1	0.9	13
3	J122549.87+332454.9	186.46	33.42	2.47	<0.01	1.1329	7.7	45.7	0.8	8
4	J113233.55+273956.3	173.14	27.67	1.65	<0.01	0.681	7.7	45.9	1.3	7
5	J130048.10+282320.6	195.20	28.39	1.04	0.01	1.929	9.3	47.3	0.7	7
6	J172255.24+320307.5	260.73	32.05	3.23	0.33	0.2752	6.8	44.7	0.8	6
7	J023410.58-085213.5	38.54	-8.87	3.46	0.33	0.992	7.1	45.1	0.7	5
8	J005324.60+123343.5	13.35	12.56	4.61	0.12	0.68	7.2	45.1	0.7	4
9	J021702.01+015352.0	34.26	1.90	3.40	<0.01	0.723	7.1	45.0	0.7	4
10	J021704.90+014935.2	34.27	1.83	3.39	0.2	0.639	6.9	44.9	0.8	4
11	J154530.23+484608.9	236.38	48.77	1.59	<0.01	0.3993	8.3	46.4	0.9	4
12	J171522.17+573626.7	258.84	57.61	2.27	0.02	2.0284	9.0	47.4	1.9	4
13	J100402.61+285535.3	151.01	28.93	1.76	<0.01	0.3287	8.2	46.4	1.4	3
14	J221715.18+002615.0	334.31	0.44	3.55	0.21	0.7532	7.4	45.5	1.1	3
15	J221738.41+001206.5	334.41	0.20	3.97	<0.01	1.1211	7.3	45.7	1.7	2
16	J022928.41-051125.0	37.37	-5.19	2.38	0.26	0.307	7.4	45.4	0.7	2
17	J074545.01+392700.9	116.44	39.45	5.69	0.02	1.6299	7.9	46.5	2.8	2
18	J114229.22+264012.4	175.62	26.67	1.75	<0.01	1.6756	8.5	46.5	0.9	2
19	J123034.20+073305.3	187.64	7.55	1.63	0.01	1.816	8.9	47.2	1.6	2
20	J140621.89+222346.5	211.59	22.40	1.93	<0.01	0.0979	7.2	45.1	0.7	2
21	J145108.76+270926.9	222.79	27.16	3.01	<0.01	0.0645	7.1	45.3	1.0	2
22	J233317.38-002303.4	353.32	-0.38	3.73	0.28	0.5129	6.8	44.9	1.0	2
23	J002209.69+013213.0	5.54	1.54	2.59	0.09	1.8826	8.7	46.7	0.8	1
24	J014634.38-093014.3	26.64	-9.50	2.72	<0.01	0.3934	7.2	45.2	0.8	1
25	J014904.48+125746.2	27.27	12.96	5.32	0.01	0.73	7.6	45.5	0.7	1
26	J015828.31-014810.0	29.62	-1.80	2.44	0.01	1.7779	8.9	47.2	1.5	1
27	J020326.22-051020.5	30.86	-5.17	1.97	0.06	0.891	8.1	46.3	1.2	1
28	J022039.48-030820.3	35.16	-3.14	2.11	0.01	0.452	7.7	45.7	0.9	1
29	J024651.91-005930.9	41.72	-0.99	3.64	<0.01	0.4679	8.1	46.4	1.5	1
30	J034000.50-051747.1	55.00	-5.30	4.20	<0.01	0.345	7.7	45.7	0.9	1
31	J081014.48+280337.1	122.56	28.06	3.14	<0.01	0.821	8.6	46.5	0.7	1
32	J081331.28+254503.0	123.38	25.75	3.82	0.08	1.5096	9.6	47.9	1.4	1
33	J083850.15+261105.4	129.71	26.18	3.18	<0.01	1.6116	9.6	47.6	0.9	1
34	J084153.99+194303.1	130.47	19.72	2.56	0.13	0.4784	7.2	45.2	0.8	1
35	J085626.07+380519.6	134.11	38.09	3.17	<0.01	0.283	7.0	44.9	0.8	1
36	J090033.50+421547.0	135.14	42.26	2.37	0.02	3.293	9.3 ^(a)	48.1 ^(b)	3.1 ^(b)	1
37	J092247.03+512038.0	140.70	51.34	1.36	<0.01	0.1597	7.0	45.2	1.3	1
38	J092943.41+004127.3	142.43	0.69	3.36	<0.01	0.5866	8.2	46.5	1.3	1
39	J093922.89+370944.0	144.85	37.16	1.11	<0.01	0.1859	7.2	45.2	0.8	1

Table A.1 (Continued).

ID	SDSS Name	RA	DEC	$N_{\text{H,gal}}$	$E(B - V)_{\text{int}}$	z	$\log(M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\odot})$	$\log(L_{\text{bol}}/\text{erg s}^{-1})$	λ_{Edd}	N_{epo}
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
40	J094033.75+462315.0	145.14	46.39	1.06	<0.01	0.696	8.3 ^(c)	46.4 ^(c)	1.1 ^(c)	1
41	J103928.14+392342.1	159.87	39.40	1.60	<0.01	1.0134	8.7	46.9	1.0	1
42	J110035.00+101027.4	165.15	10.17	2.44	<0.01	1.5873	8.6	46.8	1.3	1
43	J110312.93+414154.9	165.80	41.70	0.81	<0.01	0.402	8.3 ^(c)	46.4 ^(c)	1.0 ^(c)	1
44	J112306.33+013749.6	170.78	1.63	3.61	0.01	0.696	7.6	45.7	1.0	1
45	J112317.51+051804.0	170.82	5.30	3.23	<0.01	1.0002	9.0	47.0	0.7	1
46	J112405.15+061248.8	171.02	6.21	3.91	0.02	0.2717	7.1	45.2	1.0	1
47	J112818.49+240217.4	172.08	24.04	1.13	0.02	1.6077	8.9	46.9	0.7	1
48	J120734.62+150643.7	181.89	15.11	2.26	0.14	0.75	8.4 ^(c)	46.5 ^(c)	0.9 ^(c)	1
49	J120858.01+454035.4	182.24	45.68	1.28	<0.01	1.162	9.7	47.6	0.7	1
50	J124615.77+673032.7	191.57	67.51	1.55	0.05	1.7684	8.9	46.9	0.7	1
51	J125005.72+263107.5	192.52	26.52	0.94	<0.01	2.0476	9.8	48.2	1.7	1
52	J125216.58+052737.7	193.07	5.46	1.87	<0.01	1.9	9.4	47.6	1.2	1
53	J130112.91+590206.6	195.30	59.04	1.40	<0.01	0.476	8.5 ^(c)	46.7 ^(c)	1.2 ^(c)	1
54	J132654.95-000530.1	201.72	-0.09	1.69	0.18	3.307	9.3 ^(a)	48.3 ^(b)	2.1 ^(b)	1
55	J133618.53+101742.6	204.08	10.30	2.22	<0.01	0.5827	7.7	45.8	0.9	1
56	J135306.34+113804.7	208.28	11.63	1.69	0.03	1.633	9.4	47.4	0.9	1
57	J144741.76-020339.1	221.92	-2.06	4.16	<0.01	1.4266	8.7	46.6	0.7	1
58	J161434.67+470420.0	243.64	47.07	0.95	0.05	1.861	9.7	47.8	1.0	1
59	J162617.23+142130.8	246.57	14.36	3.93	0.04	1.6622	8.2	46.5	1.7	1
60	J163201.11+373749.9	248.00	37.63	0.83	<0.01	1.4747	9.7	47.6	0.7	1
61	J223607.68+134355.3	339.03	13.73	4.76	<0.01	0.3258	8.0	46.2	1.3	1

Notes. (1) Unique X-HESS identifier; (2) SDSS IAU name; (3) right ascension; (4) declination; (5) Galactic column density (10^{20} cm^{-2}) from the full-sky HI map by [HI4PI Collaboration et al. \(2016\)](#); (6) internal reddening measured according to the procedure in § 3.3.2 (the typical uncertainty is ~ 0.01); (7) redshift; (8) black hole mass; (9) bolometric luminosity; (10) Eddington ratio; (11) total number of available epochs. ^(a) $H\beta$ -based black hole mass measurement from [Bischetti et al. \(2017\)](#). ^(b) bolometric luminosity corrected for the orientation effects and Eddington ratio from [Vietri et al. \(2018\)](#). ^(c) refined measurements of $H\beta$ -based black hole mass, bolometric luminosity and Eddington ratio from [Marziani & Sulentic \(2014\)](#).